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Inside INFRA-ART

Newsletter #05 | March 2026

Welcome to the first newsletter of 2026!

The past months have been both dynamic and productive for the INFRA-ART Spectral Library, bringing important developments, new features, and continued growth within our community. In this issue, we share a curated overview of the latest updates across the platform. Enjoy reading!

~ the INFRA-ART Team

INFRA-ART platform relaunch

The INFRA-ART Spectral Library has entered a new stage with the release of an upgraded platform, designed to support more open, connected, and scalable research workflows. This iteration brings the service in line with the European Open Science Cloud Interoperability Framework ([EOSC IF](#)), strengthening its role as a FAIR-aligned research infrastructure.

The upgrade is the result of sustained development carried out together with [evozon](#) - our tech partner. While many of the changes are structural, users will notice a more responsive interface and more efficient ways to explore the spectral collections.

What has changed?

✦ **New domain** → <https://infra-art.eu>

The platform now operates under a new domain, reflecting its transition toward an EOSC-compliant infrastructure.

✦ **Redesigned, EOSC-aligned architecture**

A redesigned backend-API-frontend structure supports interoperability, machine-to-machine communication, and easier integration with external services.

✦ **Improved interface and navigation**

The new frontend enhances browsing, filtering, and access to datasets, while also simplifying internal data management processes.

We invite INFRA-ART users to explore the platform, test the new features, and share feedback at info@infra-art.eu. Community input is essential in shaping future developments.

New features & tools for data discovery

Advanced search tool

Finding the right sample is now faster and more flexible. An advanced search tool has been recently introduced, allowing users to refine queries using multiple filters and improve discovery of records across the growing collection of samples and analytical datasets within the INFRA-ART database.

The newly introduced advanced search tool allows users to:

- Combine multiple search criteria in a single query
- Use only the fields relevant to their needs

Results match all selected criteria for precise, targeted discovery. This functionality enables more precise exploration of the database, helping users spend less time searching and more time analyzing.

Advanced Search

← Back to basic search

🔍 Search database

Keyword(s) eg. Lapis Lazuli	Alternative name eg. PB29	Material class Select material class	Data type Select data type
Origin eg. Chile	Chemical information eg. sodium-aluminium-silicate	Sample source eg. Kremer	

Clear filters Search

FTIR peak search

Responding to strong interest from our user community, the FTIR peak search tool is now available on the INFRA-ART platform. This new feature allows users to query the spectral library using specific FTIR peak values, making it easier to identify samples with matching spectral characteristics and to navigate the database more effectively. → An initial dataset of curated peak values has been introduced for approximately 300 FTIR spectra.

All FTIR peak data are manually curated and will be progressively expanded. Given the large volume of available spectra, this process will continue over the coming months. Currently, around 30% of the existing FTIR spectra include curated peak values. This development marks an important step toward more precise and efficient spectral analysis within the platform. We invite you to test the feature and share your feedback.

FTIR peak search

🔍 Spectral Data Search

NEW UPDATE

Search by FTIR

Peak value(s) / cm⁻¹

Add peak value

Material class

Select material class

Press enter to add values between 380 and 4000

Search +/- 2 cm⁻¹ from entered values

Clear filters Search

Latest updates: new samples available

Artist Materials: White Nights

Watercolors

Our collection of professional artist materials has been expanded with a new dataset comprising 24 samples of White Nights extra fine artists' watercolors, produced by Nevskaya Palitra. These paints are characterized by a high concentration of finely ground pigments and a natural gum Arabic binder. XRF measurements are currently available, with FTIR data to be added soon. Explore the collection [here](#).

New Material Class: Restoration Materials

A new material class dedicated to restoration materials has been introduced, expanding the range of reference materials available for conservation science and heritage research. The first collection in this category includes 27 samples of retouching colors in Paraloid B72 from Kremer. Currently available datasets include XRF measurements. Explore the collection [here](#).

Recent blog articles

FAIR data, global impact: what three years of INFRA-ART usage reveal

→

Drawing on Google Analytics data, the article outlines INFRA-ART's usage from 2022 to 2025, highlighting global access, user growth, key communities, discovery patterns, data interests, and the impact of

FAIR-aligned metadata on visibility and engagement. [Read more](#)

INFRA-ART platform relaunch: building an EOSC-compliant infrastructure for FAIR spectral data

→

This article explores the recent platform relaunch, focusing on the transition toward an EOSC-aligned infrastructure. It outlines the architectural changes, and the steps taken to support better data discovery, and long-term sustainability.

[Read more](#)

FINALLY! AFTER ALL THOSE YEARS
I FINALLY FOUND
THE SOURCE OF THE DATA!

Where is the data? Challenges and barriers to research data sharing and reuse

→

The article examines persistent gaps between open science principles and practice, highlighting technical, legal, and cultural barriers that limit data sharing, and hinder effective data discovery and reuse across research communities.

[Read more](#)

INFRA-ART spectral data collections: precious, toxic, rare and other hard-to-find pigments

→

This article highlights some of the most iconic pigments in history, alongside rarer

and less accessible materials documented in the INFRA-ART database, offering a unique perspective on their role in both artistic practice and heritage science research. [Read more](#)

FAIRMap4ART – RDA Adoption story

Our [RDA Adoption Story](#) has recently been published, offering a closer look at the FAIRMap4ART project, funded under [RDA TIGER](#). Under this project, we implemented several RDA outputs to strengthen FAIR data practices and enhance the semantic interoperability of the INFRA-ART data service. These include: *Ten Principles to Improve Dataset Discoverability*, *Guidelines for Publishing Structured Metadata on the Web*, and *Guidance on Data Granularity*.

In the adoption story, we reflect on the challenges encountered, how RDA recommendations were applied in practice, and the impact of their adoption on our workflows and data services. We also share key lessons learned throughout the process. We hope this experience can support and inspire other teams working toward more FAIR and interoperable research data.

Participation @IDCC26 in Zagreb

Between 16-18 February we took part in the [20th edition of the International Digital Curation Conference](#) held in Zagreb, where we presented a poster on the FAIR journey of the INFRA-ART Spectral Library. This marked an important milestone, celebrated together with the research data curation community that has supported us along the way.

Over the past year, what began as a series of challenges has evolved into a process of learning, collaboration, and transformation, shaping the platform's development. Our poster, "Curating for Reuse: FAIR and Trustworthy Services for Interdisciplinary Data Applications," highlights how the INFRA-ART data service has progressed from a standalone database into an EOSC-aligned, open-access service supporting heritage science and related fields. → As we move forward, our focus is on consolidating these efforts and progressing toward CoreTrustSeal certification.

Stay connected

Stay updated and be part of the **INFRA-ART community**:

- [Subscribe to our newsletter](#) and share it with colleagues who may find it useful.
- Follow us on [LinkedIn](#) for real-time updates, news, and project developments.
- Explore our open resources on [Zenodo](#).

